

EdTech Innovation for Covid-19

Insights from our global call for ideas

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Authors Daniel Plaut
Alice Carter
Miranda Dixon
Taiye Salami

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This year we unexpectedly found ourselves in one big global EdTech experiment. Governments, donors, teachers, parents, and learners around the world have grappled with school closures due to the Covid-19 pandemic, and have collectively asked themselves:

“ *How can we minimise the effect of school closures on learning outcomes for children, and ensure existing inequities are not widened?* ”

Seeking to identify impactful solutions to this challenge, the EdTech Hub, along with partners from mEducation Alliance, Global Innovation Exchange and UNHCR’s Humanitarian Education Accelerator, launched a call for ideas responding to the Covid-19 school closures. We were looking for ideas that could have impact as quickly as possible, but which might also build resilience for the future and strengthen systems in the long term.

This report tells the story of this call for ideas and shares insights from our review of the 371 applications submitted. Whether you are a funder, investor, policymaker, EdTech practitioner, teacher, or learner, we hope that reading this report offers some inspiration, knowledge, solidarity, and direction as we continue to tackle the effects of Covid-19 on communities and education across the world.

What this report covers

While this report is filled with rich insights about our process and findings, we understand that you may want to cut to the chase and go directly to the section you are most interested in. Click below to skip ahead, or keep reading to get the whole picture.

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Our key takeaways

Below are our key reflections on the 371 applications we received. These are based on our theoretical framework and [the 6 Ps listed below](#). In brief, we use this to understand how an EdTech programme might perform within an education system. It considers six key aspects of the education ecosystem with which any EdTech tool must engage and integrate if it is to be successful: people, product, pedagogy, policy, place, and provision.

People

- **On metrics, we found vanity over sanity, with little data on users or impact measures.** Download numbers or the number of users reached were often cited by tech innovators who sought to impress with the reach of their tools. In reality, these figures tell us very little about whether something actually works or not.
- **Marginalised communities were targeted specifically, but not generally.** A majority of programmes were targeted at 'remote communities'. Yet, lack of access to technology or internet connection was not widely considered. Furthermore, designs which considered the needs of learners with disabilities were rare.

Product

- **Virtual learning environments (VLEs) are promising, but should everyone be building their own?** A majority of applications included platforms that serve to connect learners to content or educators virtually. However, little collaboration was evident among them.
- **Innovators assume most people have access to smart technology and the internet.** This means that the most marginalised learners continue to be left behind.

Pedagogy

- **Personalised and interactive learning is all the rage.** Over three-fourths of the tools featured in the applications included some interactive teaching and learning, or personalisation component.
- **Many tools still assume that tech + content = learning but we know more is needed.** Too many proposed interventions focused primarily on getting learners access to their specific technology, without much thought as to how learning might be fostered.

Policy

- **While some applicants partner with MoEs, too often, tools work in parallel to education systems.** Instead of building on existing efforts to implement distance learning, most interventions sought to build efforts in parallel with public provision.

Place

- **The largest number of programmes are working in sub-Saharan Africa (42%) and South Asia (19%),** with Nigeria (15%) and India (13%) being the hottest countries for EdTech.
- **Community-led design of tools can lead to strong uptake and use.** By designing in collaboration with users, interventions are likely to quickly identify potential barriers to use, and ensure their tools' relevance.

Provisions

- **User fees were rare, removing one potential barrier to access for learners.** Over 70% of tools were completely free, 4% offered some free functionality, and just under 25% required paid subscriptions or pay-per-use models.
- **Sustainability. What's that?** Lack of clarity on the sustainability of the tools' business models was a general trend.

- **Funding and partnership were the most often cited needs.** Yet, reviewers felt that additional pedagogical expertise, as well as research and experimentation support, might be important.

Background to the call for ideas

With 188 countries having closed their schools this year, [Covid-19 has affected over 1.6 billion children](#). This is on top of the 258 million learners who were out of school before the outbreak. In the longer-term, after the immediate crisis response has passed and schools begin to reopen, we continue to feel the consequences of school closures, such as:

- Continued disruption of learner enrolment and retention in school;
- Negative impacts on the cognitive, academic, and socio-emotional development of learners;
- Stalled or even reversed learning gains in affected regions;
- Reduced educational attainment of marginalised children, such as girls, children with disabilities, and those in refugee camps, and internally displaced communities in particular.

Unfortunately, we know that these impacts will be especially felt and more difficult to recover from in lower-income environments across Africa, Asia, and the Middle East. As EdTech Hub, we felt we could play a role in identifying and supporting promising interventions to address this crisis.

That's why in April 2020, we launched [a global call for ideas](#) in partnership with mEducation Alliance and Global Innovation Exchange. The call was open to organisations from anywhere in the world so that we might surface the most promising and innovative ideas.

Our offer to applicants

1. An invitation to pitch to funders at Covid-19 EdTech Pitch Days, enabling exposure to a global network of education donors and investors.
2. Connections to world-leading experts for how best to adapt and scale promising ideas for addressing education during the Covid-19 pandemic.
3. Opportunity to be selected for an EdTech Hub sandbox.

The call invited submissions addressing a whole range of issues emerging from the pandemic. From solutions that reach out-of-school learners and those in non-formal settings, to those that support teachers, school education leaders, parents and community actors in their responses to the crisis. We were open to ideas that address the psychosocial and socio-emotional impacts of Covid-19 on learners, or ‘learning-adjacent’ needs such as feeding programmes and the provision of safe spaces.

How we reviewed the applications

Applications first passed through an initial sift (intended to eliminate approaches which were out of scope, or did not sufficiently focus on education outcomes). Following this first round, remaining applications were each reviewed by two separate EdTech experts. Expert reviewers included members of EdTech Hub, mEducation Alliance, Global Innovation Exchange (GIE), UNHCR and other partner organisations.

In order to sort through the wealth of applications we received, each was rated from 0–6 on the following criteria:

- Proof of impact through existing evidence, real-life use or testing with users.
- Potential to scale through partnerships, replication, or revenue models.
- Designed or able to impact stakeholders in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), marginalised communities, and those in low-resource contexts.
- Team members seem capable and / or have a track record of experience, and will work fast, be adaptive and collaborative.
- Unique approaches to solving a long-standing or previously intractable

problem.

- Potential to strengthen education systems in the longer term.

We invited some of the highest-scoring applicants to present at four Pitch Days, in front of an audience of funders, investors, and experts from the EdTech sector which we called the Action Committee. This Action Committee included representatives from The World Bank, USAID, Overseas Development Institute, UNHCR, BRAC, and Foreign, Commonwealth and Development Office (FCDO). Each Pitch Day included a facilitated discussion between the members of the Action Committee, to discuss whether to, and ways to, support the interventions being presented. You can read more about the Pitch Days on our website.

At the end of our review process, we had:

Seeking to draw insights for the broader EdTech ecosystem, our team conducted a detailed analysis of these applications using two methods — a quantitative analysis of the data from across the applications, and qualitative analysis of insights from a series of sense-making workshops with those who reviewed the applications.

Our theoretical framework

We see ‘Edtech’ as only one part of a solution, existing within a broader system of factors that need to work together to make impact at scale. Throughout our work we push ourselves to consider the full breadth of the education system, and what it would take to really improve learning outcomes for the most marginalised.

When technology is introduced into education systems, it does not exist in isolation.

In order to consider how an EdTech programme might perform within an education system, we have developed a framework which considers six key aspects of the education ecosystem (6 Ps) with which any EdTech tool must engage and integrate to be successful: people, product, pedagogy, policy, place, and provision.

The 6 Ps framework allows us to consistently evaluate the promise of each EdTech solution, while still accounting for the complexity involved in innovating within education systems. By applying this same lens to the 371 applications reviewed through our call for ideas, we hoped to draw out key insights about the broader EdTech response to Covid-19. These are presented below, organised around each of our 6 Ps.

What we learnt

People

To what extent has the proposed tool engaged with its users? How have learners and caretakers, or those responsible for implementing a tool, been considered in programme design?

On metrics, we found vanity over sanity, with little data on user or impact measures

Download numbers or the number of users reached were often cited by tech innovators who sought to impress with the reach of their tools. Although vanity measures might sound impressive, in reality, they tell us very little about whether something actually works or not. Very few programmes cited:

- Data on user testing and user experience, making it clear that they lacked familiarity with our target beneficiary communities.
- Evidence of impact on learning outcomes. Of the six criteria used in rating the quality of applications, programmes averaged the lowest score on the level of evidence they had to back up their pitches.

In some ways this is not surprising, many of the ideas featured in our call were pivoting their standard approach to try something new within the context of Covid-19, and may not have had a chance to evaluate their impact. However, our expert reviewers were surprised to find that very few applications included *any* data that demonstrated user engagement (user testing, user satisfaction surveys, etc.) or data from evaluations conducted prior to the shift to response to the Covid-19 pandemic.

Advice to those working in EdTech: if you're pivoting an approach, this is best done with users and in line with impact. While it's hard to get long-term measures for learning outcomes overnight, we can measure proxy indicators or signals that this pivot is worthwhile.

Marginalised communities were targeted specifically, but not generally

More than half (54%) of programmes were targeted at remote communities, a demographic that includes rural, low-resourced settings, as well as refugee and IDP settlements. We also saw a number of promising innovations targeting specific marginalised communities, such as girls and women, refugees affected by conflict, and learners with disabilities. Below we feature two examples of interventions specifically designed to address such communities, deaf learners and those living in 'off-grid' areas, and that have done so by working closely with those communities to ensure their interventions have the learning outcomes they aim to achieve.

Operational for over 25 years, the **Deaf Reach Program** runs seven schools across Pakistan that cater to more than 1,200 deaf children and their families. They've created the first ever digital Pakistan Sign Language dictionary and other sign language resources which are online and available countrywide. To ensure their students are able to continue learning through the prolonged period of school closures, Deaf Reach has distributed laptops loaded with digital curricular resources in sign language to over 200 of their learners. In addition, Deaf Reach will conduct home visits by teachers to provide parents and caretakers with guidance on how to foster learning at home.

In Uganda, **Sun Books** aims to improve literacy outcomes for children in 'off-the-grid' areas by distributing tablets preloaded with educational content as well as a solar charger panel unit. Children can access 600 e-books with stories to promote values and 300 games to enjoy while learning to read and write. The content has been developed collaboratively with local teachers and learners to ensure that it has the learning outcomes they want to see.

In spite of these and other interventions targeting marginalised communities, the majority of call for ideas' applicants did not explicitly design for accessibility or inclusion. For instance, learners with disabilities were only the explicit focus of a handful of ideas (some featured in our 'Learners with Disabilities' pitch day).

While not a primary audience for all interventions, we would urge each and every idea to take steps to make their tools more accessible to learners with special needs. Existing guidance for making EdTech tools more inclusive has been codified in USAID's [Universal Design for Learning \(UDL\) Toolkit](#) ([↑Hayes, et al., 2018](#)) and in the EdTech Hub's own brief on [EdTech for special](#)

educational needs and / or disabilities (SEND) ([↑Coflan & Kaye, 2020](#)) in low- and middle-income countries.

Product

What are the technical components of a proposed intervention? How does the tech work? What are key components of its technical requirements and user design?

Virtual learning environments (VLEs) are promising, but should everyone be building their own?

Many applications were stand-alone virtual learning environments often also referred to as learning management systems (LMS), which generally serve to virtually connect learners to learning content or educators. 69% of the tools submitted to our call for ideas were focused on disseminating 'learning content', with the remaining 19% and 12% providing education management and communications / collaboration tools, respectively. VLEs have been shown to be particularly relevant during the Covid-19 crisis.

"Platforms that offer VLEs provide facilitators with tools and resources to support education delivery. Facilitators (including teachers) can design VLEs to serve multiple purposes and functions. During the immediate crisis, VLEs can provide out-of-school students with an alternative platform to access quality educational content and to pursue national learning objectives ...VLEs can give learners access to educational resources, connect students with teachers and facilitate remote lessons." ([↑McBurnie, 2020](#))

Given their potential to reach out-of-school learners, it makes sense that VLEs would be the most commonly cited approach in responding to the Covid-19 crisis. However, the wide proliferation of proprietary VLE platforms, features, and learning content suggests they are often starting from scratch, rather than adapting or building on existing models. As noted by [↑McBurnie \(2020\)](#), implementers can and should first attempt to repurpose VLEs to reduce the time and cost of software and content development. Many existing VLE *"systems allow implementers to use readily available curriculum-aligned materials, incorporate supplementary resources and upload their own content."* (ibid.) Adapting from existing platforms would be especially beneficial to those addressing the urgency brought on by Covid-19.

Innovators assume most people have access to smart technology and the internet, which means the most marginalised learners continue to be left behind. Nearly 78% of the applications also assume users have access to smartphones, tablets, or personal computers (PCs). In addition, nearly 60% of

ideas required full online functionality, while an additional 30% required partial online connection. These tech requirements present a major barrier to learners in low-resource settings, who might not have access to these gadgets, easily available and consistent access to an internet connection, or the funds to pay for it.

Internet connectivity required by tools

However, there are many interventions that overcome this barrier through developing offline solutions. Some of the most promising global VLEs (such as Kolibri, Open Learning Exchange, and others) have full or partial offline usability, to ensure marginalised learners can still access learning content regardless of connectivity. Of the offline innovations that applied to the call, several were selected for our ‘Learning Offline’ pitch day, including Mavis Talking Books, featured below.

Mavis Talking Books aims to provide basic education to learners across Africa without access to the internet. Learners use the battery-powered Mavis pen to tap on pages of the Mavis Book to activate audio lessons and exercises in a language they can understand. It can store up to one hundred (100) Mavis Book programmes in it and has 10 hours of battery life. Mavis Books recognises the impact of learning together so the technology is designed to support learners working in groups as well as individually.

Pedagogy

Are tools or interventions designed with sound pedagogical principles? To what extent has a tool demonstrated it can meaningfully improve learning outcomes?

Personalised and interactive learning is all the rage

Nearly 77% of the tools featured in our call for ideas' applications included some interactive teaching and learning, or a personalisation component. This means they go beyond dissemination of content to also building in mechanisms to gather data on the users' performance and adapt their design or lessons accordingly.

This approach is in line with one of the most promising pedagogical EdTech approaches, personalised adaptive learning (PAL), which adapts learning opportunities and instruction to individual capabilities. A recent rapid evidence review of personalised learning conducted by the EdTech hub found that *“technology-supported personalised learning appears to offer significant promise to improve learning outcomes, including potentially ‘out-of-class’ and ‘out-of-school’ learning”* (↑Major & Francis, 2020). The closure of schools due to the Covid-19 pandemic makes this approach additionally promising.

Mindspark is a technology-based adaptive learning programme that allows learners to learn and practise maths and language. It can be used in in-school and out-of-school contexts. The software includes continuous learner assessment, instructional games, videos, and activities from which learners learn through explanations and feedback. It is being used for over 700,000 registered learners from high-fee private schools and for over 40,000 learners in government schools across India, both in their homes and at school.

One of the common ways innovators are incorporating personalisation and feedback into their tech tools is through gamification, examples include Curious Learning and GraphoGame, both featured below.

Curious Learning works with partners to curate, localise, distribute, and measure free open-source learning apps using gamification. These include Feed the Monster, a game which teaches learners to learn 45 letter sounds in their language. When UNICEF tested Feed the Curious Monster with Syrian refugees they learnt that 22 hours of exposure is equal to 2 months of literacy learning in a well-resourced school.

GraphoGame is an academically researched learning app, game, and methodology for teaching kindergarten and primary-school children early grade literacy in English, Chinese, Dutch and many other languages. It is designed to engage learners with fun features that children are used to using in mobile games. Taking inspiration from role-playing games, the child creates their own avatar that grows with them and gives them a sense of ownership in their learning.

While extremely promising, PAL approaches often have limitations in terms of cost and their ability to scale. Generally, most PAL tools require 1-1 engagement between a learner and device which in many contexts can be prohibitive in terms of cost.

Many tools assume that tech + content = learning, but we know more is needed

Reviewers of our applications felt that too many proposed interventions focused primarily on getting learners access to their specific technology, without much thought as to how learning might be fostered or how they might know it had been. This is especially salient during the Covid-19 pandemic, when millions of learners are being forced to engage with learning content at home. Promising initiatives included wrap-around services

(beyond the tech alone), such as training on tool use, guidance for parental engagement, follow-up visits by teachers, community facilitation, or collection of feedback by short messaging service (SMS) to ensure that the content or tool that is shared has the best chance of achieving the desired learning outcomes. Mango Tree Literacy Lab's radio instruction programme, featured below, is an example of an intervention that thinks holistically about its dissemination of content.

Mango Tree Literacy Lab (MTLL)

responded to Covid-19 school closures in Uganda by pivoting their proven in-school literacy approach to radio in order to give parents and learners the support needed to continue learning at home. Long-utilised literacy tools, teaching methods, and classroom materials, were converted into weekly radio programmes. While they have confidence in their methods and have received positive feedback on their radio programming, Mango Tree believes that dissemination of content alone (in this case radio lessons) will not lead to improved learning. To ensure learners get the most out of their programme, they have created 'listening centres' where community members gather to safely listen to broadcasts together. In addition, Mango Tree has produced and disseminated a co-teacher guidebook to instruct parents, older siblings, and caretakers on how to facilitate follow-on learning activities such as songs and games. This reinforces the concepts taught in radio lessons.

Policy

How do tech tools engage with the broader policy environment? Do they seek to complement, improve, and partner with government responses to Covid-19?

While some applicants partner with MoEs, too often tools work in parallel to education systems

Instead of building on existing efforts to implement distance learning alongside ministries of education, proposed EdTech interventions we received

through the call are often seeking to build separate processes by engaging with learners outside of the public sector. This was particularly the case with some of the virtual learning platforms. Overall, only 22% of applicants were noted to feature national curriculum-aligned learning content in their platforms. At a time of crisis, when distance learning might be the only medium for ensuring public curriculum content reaches learners, our reviewers hoped to see more extensive collaboration between public and private education providers. However, those that did link up with education systems offered fascinating models for what EdTech integration into the education system can look like, Rising on Air being a key example.

Rising on Air, is a partnership between the Rising Schools Academy (a private education provider) and the Sierra Leone Ministry of Education. This collaboration has its roots in a previous crisis: the ebola pandemic of 2013–15, when schools were closed and

distance learning through radio was seen as one of the only options. Today, radio lessons have been expanded significantly to address closures due to Covid-19. Rising Schools Academies' direct link to government, as well as their eagerness to collaborate with education providers of all kinds during this crisis has led to the development of a broader network of radio instruction, that now spans across five ministries of education, and over 30 implementing organisations who share scripts for radio lessons, best practices, and problem solve together through their community of practice known as 'Collaborators on Air'.

The logo for 'Rising on Air' features the word 'RISING' in a bold, black, sans-serif font at the top. Below it, the words 'ON • AIR' are enclosed in a black rectangular border, with a small black dot between 'ON' and 'AIR'.

Place

Where is the intervention being delivered? What are the local needs and how have they been incorporated into the programme's design?

The largest number of programmes are working in sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia, with Nigeria and India being the hottest countries for EdTech

42% of programmes submitted to the call are being implemented in sub-Saharan Africa and 19% are being implemented in South Asia.

Applications across geographic regions

Within these regions, 18% and 15% of the programmes were developed in Nigeria and India respectively (the highest of any countries). While their prominence in our process may be influenced by the EdTech Hub's own relationships and networks in these two countries, it is nevertheless indicative of the vibrant EdTech ecosystems in both countries.

The number of 'homegrown' programmes (those founded in their target communities) was also high. Once again, the programmes' headquarters were most often found in Nigeria (15%) and India (13%). That said, global EdTech leaders in the global north also produced a significant number of tools, including the United States with 11% and the United Kingdom with 6%. While the global north continues to have a major influence on the form and function of EdTech, innovators based in the global south are on the rise. This is a significant development, which points to increased integration between tech developers and the communities they work with.

Community-led design of tools can lead to strong uptake and use

Some of the more impressive tools included in applications in response to our call were those designed hand in hand with the communities they serve. By designing with their users, these interventions were likely to quickly identify potential barriers to use, ensuring their tools' relevance. These applicants also demonstrated a close understanding of the challenges faced by their users. Two Rabbits, featured below, offers a compelling example of how learning content and tech tools can be designed alongside beneficiary communities.

Two Rabbits engages communities to record interactive, audio, preschool lessons in the local language, uploads them onto SD cards that can be replayed on an mp3 device, and trains community members to facilitate learning.

They propose adapting this model for a Covid-19 response by 1) recording training sessions for caregivers to facilitate learning; 2) distributing SD cards to families to play on cell phones at home; 3) mobilising teachers to provide door-to-door distanced support. With the help of parents, children and community organisations, the Two Rabbits model was designed for the semi-nomadic hunter-gatherers in Baka, Cameroon, by creating an interactive audio programme in the local language. The programme features singing, games, and folklore of the Baka community.

Provisions

How are initiatives funded? To what extent are their business models sustainable? What other needs do they have?

User fees were rare, removing one potential barrier to access for learners

Over 70% of tools were completely free, with an additional 4% offering some free functionality, and just under 25% requiring paid subscriptions or pay-per-use models. While most tools did not charge users, additional cost barriers to use for many tools included access to the appropriate hardware and internet data.

User cost for tools

Sustainability. What's that?

Lack of clarity on the sustainability of some EdTech business models was a general trend. Reviewers were left with many questions about the ability of initiatives to remain self-sustaining while ensuring access was possible for the most marginalised learners. Little consideration appeared to be given to the long-term maintenance of the EdTech tools (once they were distributed), or to continuous support for users in how they might make use of software and learning content on a continuous basis. Some models, such as Tiny Totos featured below, offered creative strategies for sustainability, but these were the exception, not the rule.

Tiny Totos is a social enterprise working with daycare entrepreneurs in Nairobi slums to provide safe and affordable daycare for preschool children. Sustainability is one of its core principles: the organisation provides

training and investment to child care providers designed to upgrade their standards or performance, diversify their income, and ensure sustainability of their businesses. For example: Tiny Totos finances smartphones as well as stoves that daycare providers use in preparing meals that are sold to children within their care, helping these providers to raise revenue to support their operations.

Funding and partnership were the most often cited needs

39% of interventions requested funding and cited this as their primary need. 22% identified trusted partnerships as their biggest barrier. Many looked to collaborate with members of the EdTech Hub or pitch day 'Action Committee' (including donors) to help them market and distribute their technology in their target communities, or scale them into new contexts and languages.

While these were the most often cited needs by applicants, in general our panel of reviewers felt that additional pedagogical expertise, as well as research and experimentation support might also be appropriate needs (and in some cases more pressing). The gaps mentioned above, ranging from a lack of consideration for users' experience or satisfaction with tools, to the frequent assumption that accessibility of their tool alone is likely to lead to learning, demonstrated that many applicants were not quite ready to make effective use of additional funding or support to scale.

Recommendations and next steps

...for EdTech practitioners

- Test your tool early and often with users, however small the group. This data will help you to iterate your model and increase your chances of reaching impact at scale.
- As possible, look to integrate inclusivity into your product from the get go. How might you be able to remove access barriers for learners with disabilities, living in remote or low-resource settings, or with limited access to technology? Tools will not be able to reach every learner, but this doesn't mean they should not do their best to be inclusive.
- Integrate your product within existing provision to strengthen (rather than compete with) education systems. Where possible, align the content of your tool with education content from the government curriculum.
- Look to see how learning can be personalised and interactive. Build in feedback loops, to provide guidance to learners, or play-based features to keep them engaged.
- Focus on measuring user experience, satisfaction, and learning outcomes, not just vanity metrics such as number of users or downloads.
- Grow partnerships within your target community, especially if you are not based in it and consider developing tools alongside community members.

- Build a sustainable path to scale by exploring creative and new business models that will ensure your product is both inclusive and financially sustainable.

...for funders, policymakers and EdTech system experts

- Incentivise data collection on actual user experiences and assessment of learning outcomes or relevant proxies when supporting and funding EdTech initiatives.
- Look to facilitate integration of products within existing education systems.
- Incentivise building EdTech products that specifically target the most marginalised learners and or seek to minimise their potential barriers to access.
- Encourage and invest in tools that go beyond learning content dissemination alone, and include wrap-around services, engage with target communities, and experiment with personalised and interactive learning.
- Build ecosystems of EdTech that incentivise initiatives to learn from one another, share data and collaborate.
- Encourage development of EdTech interventions that are designed with inclusivity, accessibility, and sustainability strategies.

...what we're doing next:

- The 250 applications reviewed after the first round of reviews will be considered for inclusion in the Global Innovation Exchange database, as well as looped into events related to the mEducation Alliance Symposium.
- The Innovations Works team at the EdTech Hub are aiming to launch six Covid-19 response sandboxes in 2020–2021. Two of the selected sandbox candidates have already been sourced from our call for ideas' pipeline, with more still to come.
- Evidence sourced from Covid-19 sandbox engagements will be compiled and shared in our next brief.

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